

Action of Alkali on Azobenzene-2-sulphenyl Bromide

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Syntheses of azobenzene-2-sulphenyl bromide (I) and its derivatives as well as their properties and reactions have recently been reported^{1,2}. Actions of aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate, aqueous sodium hydroxide, and liquid ammonia on azobenzene-2-sulphenyl bromide have also been discussed³. In order to obtain further information about the action of alkali, the reactions of potassium and lithium hydroxides and of sodium, potassium, and lithium carbonates on the said compound have been investigated.

Azobenzene-2-sulphenyl bromide, which in aqueous solution exists as true salts involving 2-phenylbenzo-1-thia-2,3-diazonium ions (II)⁴, forms on addition of an excess of potassium or lithium hydroxide the water-soluble, blue-violet potassium or lithium sulphenate, which could not be isolated. The corresponding sodium sulphenate has been identified by conversion to the stable methyl-2-phenylazophenyl sulphoxide on rapid treatment with methyl sulphate by Burawoy and Chaudhuri³.

On keeping, the blue colour of the solution disappears, the sulphenate being replaced by di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphide and di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphoxide and azobenzene-2-sulphinic acid. Addition of sodium, lithium, or potassium carbonate produces no violet colour, but yields a precipitate of the corresponding disulphide and disulphoxide, which can be separated by chromatography. The filtrate contains a small quantity of alkali sulphinates which is recovered as azobenzene-2-sulphinic acid on acidification and subsequent extraction with ether. This is due to the further action of alkali on the disulphoxide, which is comparatively unstable. The reaction takes place according to equations (1) and (2):

(where Ar = C₆H₅NNC₆H₄)

1. Burawoy and Vellins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 90.

2. Burawoy and Chaudhuri, *ibid.*, 1958, 648.

3. *Idem, ibid.*, 1958, 653.

4. Burawoy *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 4481.

If the reaction mixture is allowed to stand for a considerable length of time, a fourth product, in addition to the other three already mentioned, is obtained. This is possibly due to decomposition of di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphoxide to di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) sulphide and sulphur dioxide:

This is somewhat similar to the decomposition of di-(2-phenylazo-1-naphthyl) disulphoxide which, however, is very unstable and decomposes even on keeping at the room temperature³.

1% Aqueous solution of potassium carbonate (50 ml) was slowly added to a saturated aqueous solution of azobenzene-2-sulphenyl bromide (100 ml) with constant stirring. An orange-coloured colloidal solution resulted. On keeping it for a few hours (or on immediate salting out with AnalaR sodium chloride), an orange precipitate of di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphide and di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphoxide came out, which was filtered, dried, and dissolved in benzene. The benzene solution was then chromatographed on a column of silica gel. The disulphide passed quickly through the column and was recovered from the benzene solution. Crystallisation from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) furnished orange needles, m.p. 142° (Burawoy and Vellins' report m.p. 142°). The disulphoxide adsorbed at the top of the column was eluted with chloroform and recovered. Crystallisation from light petroleum provided orange needles, m.p. 103° (lit.² m.p. 103-104°).

The aqueous filtrate was acidified with HCl and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the solvent yielded azobenzene-2-sulphinic acid, crystallised from dilute methanol in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 104° (lit.¹ m.p. 104°).

The experiment was repeated and the product allowed to stand for 72 hr. The orange precipitate was chromatographed as before. The benzene solution was found to contain a mixture of disulphide and monosulphide, which was separated by fractional crystallisation. The di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) disulphide (m.p. 142°) crystallised first. The more soluble di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) sulphide was recovered from benzene and finally crystallised from light petroleum in yellow needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 4.3; the formula requires C, 73.09; H, 4.56%). Molecular weight of di-(*o*-phenylazophenyl) sulphide, determined by X-ray method from measurement of cell-dimensions and density, was found to be 397, calc. value being 394.

Similar results were obtained with sodium and lithium carbonate. With potassium and lithium hydroxide, the final results were the same as above, but the reaction was initiated by the appearance of a blue-violet colour which disappeared on keeping.

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